

Progressive Airflow Obstruction: Bronchiolitis Obliterans in DIPNECH with Pulmonary Carcinoid – A Longitudinal Case Report

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Abstract

Diffuse idiopathic pulmonary neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia (DIPNECH) is a rare pulmonary condition that can progress to carcinoid tumours and small airway obstruction. We report a 48-year-old woman with biopsy-confirmed DIPNECH and a typical carcinoid tumour who developed progressive fixed airflow obstruction consistent with bronchiolitis obliterans. Despite multiple comorbidities, including thyroid carcinoma and adrenal insufficiency, her condition stabilised with inhaled therapy, macrolide prophylaxis, and pulmonary rehabilitation. This case highlights the diagnostic challenge of DIPNECH, often mislabelled as asthma or COPD, and the importance of multidisciplinary, long-term follow-up focusing on functional outcomes and quality of life.

Background

Diffuse idiopathic pulmonary neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia (DIPNECH) is a rare and under-recognised pulmonary disorder, primarily affecting middle-aged, non-smoking women. It is characterised by diffuse proliferation of neuroendocrine cells within the bronchial epithelium, which may manifest as tumourlets or carcinoid tumours. Patients often present with chronic cough and dyspnoea and are frequently misdiagnosed with obstructive airway diseases such as asthma or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). The disease course is variable, ranging from stable indolent disease to progressive small airway obstruction and bronchiolitis obliterans. Optimal management remains uncertain, though options include somatostatin analogues, inhaled therapy, and supportive measures.

Case Presentation

A 48-year-old woman presented with a decade-long history of persistent cough and exertional dyspnoea. She was a lifelong non-smoker with no relevant environmental or

occupational exposures. Initial diagnoses of asthma and later COPD were made in the community, but she showed minimal response to standard inhaled therapy. A video-assisted thoracoscopic biopsy was performed in 2016 due to progressive symptoms and multiple bilateral nodules on CT, confirming DIPNECH with a background typical carcinoid tumour and associated neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia.

Investigations

Serial pulmonary function tests demonstrated progressive, fixed airflow obstruction, with FEV₁ declining from 2.1 L (70% predicted) to 1.2 L (40% predicted) over five years, despite a preserved diffusion capacity (DLCO 85% predicted). High-resolution CT scans revealed bilateral pulmonary nodules (2–6 mm), mosaic attenuation, and air trapping, consistent with bronchiolitis obliterans. There was no evidence of metastatic disease. Comorbidities identified during follow-up included papillary thyroid carcinoma, adrenal adenoma, secondary adrenal insufficiency, burning mouth syndrome, and chronic upper airway disease.

Differential Diagnosis

- Obstructive airway disease (asthma/COPD)
- Bronchiolitis obliterans (post-infectious or autoimmune)
- Hypersensitivity pneumonitis
- Diffuse idiopathic pulmonary neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia (DIPNECH)

Asthma and COPD were excluded due to lack of reversibility and normal diffusion capacity, while hypersensitivity pneumonitis was ruled out by negative serology and absence of exposure history. The presence of mosaic attenuation, small nodules, and histological evidence of neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia confirmed DIPNECH complicated by bronchiolitis obliterans.

Treatment

The patient commenced Lanreotide (somatostatin analogue) but discontinued it after several months due to gastrointestinal side effects, despite initial symptomatic improvement in cough. Ongoing management included an inhaled corticosteroid and long-acting β_2 -agonist combination, long-term azithromycin prophylaxis, and pulmonary rehabilitation. She received supportive care for recurrent respiratory infections and two episodes of COVID-19. Her treatment was coordinated through a multidisciplinary team, involving respiratory, endocrinology, and ENT specialists, to address her comorbidities and optimise quality of life.

Outcome and Follow-Up

Over nine years of follow-up, the patient developed progressive airflow limitation, though her condition has stabilised clinically and radiologically in recent years. FEV₁ has remained stable at 1.2–1.3 L, and CT scans have shown no new nodules or progression. She reports persistent fatigue and functional limitation but has remained free of major exacerbations.

Discussion

This case illustrates the slowly progressive yet clinically challenging course of DIPNECH complicated by a carcinoid tumour and bronchiolitis obliterans. Fixed airflow obstruction in DIPNECH reflects small airway fibrosis rather than reversible bronchospasm, explaining the poor response to bronchodilators. Somatostatin analogues such as Lanreotide or Octreotide may reduce cough and stabilise radiological progression in some patients, though tolerability and efficacy vary. Macrolide prophylaxis and pulmonary rehabilitation can help improve symptoms and reduce exacerbation frequency. Airway obstruction in DIPNECH is believed to result from bronchiolar wall fibrosis secondary to neuroendocrine cell proliferation and inflammation. Trials of somatostatin analogues and mTOR inhibitors are ongoing, but evidence remains limited. Clinicians should maintain awareness of DIPNECH as a potential cause of unexplained fixed airflow obstruction in non-smokers, as timely diagnosis can prevent unnecessary corticosteroid exposure and facilitate appropriate follow-up.

Learning Points

1. Suspect DIPNECH in middle-aged, non-smoking women with chronic cough and unexplained fixed obstruction.
2. Histology confirms diagnosis and identifies associated carcinoid tumours.
3. Bronchiolitis obliterans contributes to irreversible airflow limitation.
4. Somatostatin analogues, macrolide prophylaxis, and rehabilitation may stabilise disease and improve quality of life.

Keywords

DIPNECH, carcinoid tumour, bronchiolitis obliterans, fixed airflow obstruction, somatostatin analogue

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